

Effect of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This paper investigated Effects of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses guided the work. The study adopted descriptive research design. 1,941 teachers in the nine educational zone of the State, constituted the population. A sample size of 332 participants took part in the study. This sample was randomly selected from a population of 1,941 subjects. The rationale for the use of the sample was justified by applying the Yamane's (1967) formula to the population of 1,941 to obtain a minimum sample size of 332. The major research instrument that was used for the study is the questionnaire titled: —Effects of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State Questionnaire (EFAASPSBSQ). The Likert methods of summated ratings were used in drafting the questionnaire for the study. Each item in the cluster is constructed on a – 4-point rating scale of very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), low extent (LE) and very low extent (VLE) weighted 4-1 respectively. The instrument was validated by the experts in Educational Foundation and Measurement and Evaluation departments from the Rivers State University. The test-retest method was applied to ensure that the instrument is reliable. The instruments were administered to respondents in secondary schools outside Bayelsa State, who were not part of the study. The results were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to ascertain the coefficient at 0.80. Out of 332 copies of the questionnaire administered to the respondents, 330 was retrieved and used for the study. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested using the z- test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. When the calculated z was less than the critical z of ± 1.96 the null hypothesis was accepted but when the calculated z was more than the Critical z of ± 1.96 the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld. Findings show that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of Male and Female teachers on the extent to which 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The study therefore, recommended among others, the States governments should sensitize the communities on insuring educational institutions. Schools should engage qualified professionals to assess school buildings, design, construct and maintain school facilities to be resilient in the face of recurrent floods and other weather-related disasters.

Keywords: Academic Activities, Bayelsa State, Effects, 2022 Flooding, Public, Students, Secondary Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The frequency and severity of climate-related disasters like floods and droughts are significantly impacted by the current climatic variability. One of the most frequent and harmful natural disasters that cause substantial damage is flooding. Infrastructure, governmental and private services, the environment, the economy, and human settlements are all negatively impacted (Bakker, 2021). In the last ten years, there have been devastating floods in a number of countries, including Bangladesh, China, India, Germany, the United States, Malawi, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. Flood losses are the most common hydro- meteorological disasters in East Africa and have hampered economic progress in both industrialized and emerging nations.

Floods become a disaster when an event seriously disrupts the functioning of a community or society and results in significant human, material, economic, or environmental losses that are greater than the capacity of the affected society to cope using its own resources. Floods are a problem when the magnitude and impacts of their occurrence exceed the capacity of affected communities to cope (United Nations International Strategy, 2022). Flooding has an impact on many areas of the economy in Sub-Saharan Africa, including education, agriculture, cattle, transportation, housing, public health, industrial processing, and tourism. The effects have serious political and socioeconomic ramifications.

Disasters not only impact people but can also rip apart the social fabric of entire nations (Dida, Gicher, Olado, Anyona, Matano & Ofulla, 2021). The most frequent environmental disaster, flooding consistently results in about 20,000 fatalities annually and negatively impacts almost 75 million people. One of the main challenges preventing Africa's expanding population from escaping poverty is flooding (Matiki, 2022).

In Nigeria, these hazards have increased in number, frequency and complexity. The level of destruction has also become more severe with more deaths of people and animals, loss of livelihoods, destruction of infrastructure among other effects resulting in losses of varying magnitude. Education as a human right is universal and inalienable and is especially important in enabling people to reach their full potential and exercise other rights. This right does not disappear or get suspended because of disasters and emergencies. When education is

interrupted or limited, students drop out, with negative and permanent economic and social impacts for students, their families, and their communities. (Matiki, 2022) further observes that flooding has a negative impact on school attendance because school children cannot cross flooded rivers. Floods also result in the destruction of water and sanitation infrastructure. This has negative impacts on schools as a result of coming into contact with contaminated water that increases the prevalence of water-related diseases and this leads to chronic absenteeism which hampers learning.

Quality education offers physical, psychological, and cognitive protection that can preserve dignity, sustain, and save lives from emergency situations through recovery (Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies, 2022). The secondary school net enrolment rate in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, is about high. Millions of students routinely miss an entire school year due to yearly occurring floods (United Nations Children Fund, 2021). The most crucial element for attaining sustainable development is commonly hailed as education, which is also employed as a key tool for altering attitudes and behavior. This is acknowledged by the Hyogo Framework for Action, which encourages governments and civil society to use education, which promotes knowledge and creativity, to create a climate of safety and resilience throughout the country (Turnbull & Street, 2021). One way that floods can prevent people from achieving their educational goals is by destroying schools. Therefore, in the twenty-first century, safeguarding students and schools against natural disasters is crucial (Achoka & Maiyo, 2022).

The majority of the natural disasters that affect Bayelsa state are weather-related, including floods, droughts, and severe winds (United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction, 2022). These dangers have recently grown in size, frequency, and complexity. Floods can effectively destroy decades of infrastructure development, severely impair economic prosperity, and cause diseases and fatalities in less developed states like Bayelsa. The most vulnerable individuals of society are where the majority of these deaths occur (Achoka & Maiyo, 2022). Floods in Bayelsa have an effect on the local government areas of Sagbama, Ekeremor, Southern Ijaw, Ogbia, Yenagoa, Nembe, and Kolokuma Opokuma. In most cases, a variety of steps must be performed to prevent the floods. When the rains peaked between September and October, many of the roads and bridges linking Bayelsa with other neighboring states were cut off, rendering the people helpless. As of the end of October, PREMIUM TIMES, 2022 observed that the East-West Road, the sole access to and from the state between Ughelli and Patani in Delta State, as well as Okogbe and Ahoada in Rivers State, collapsed with a high volume of flood water occupying the stretch.

The floods were so devastating that trucks and vehicles conveying food items such as garri, tomatoes, onions, beans, rice, poultry products and fuel could not access Bayelsa state. In the Azikoro area of the state, corpses from submerged cemeteries around the area surfaced on floating waters on streets in the state capital, raising fears of an epidemic. In October, efforts to visit the affected morgues at Bomadi General Hospital and Olodiana were futile as the roads were submerged by water. The flood was so devastating that the country home of former President Goodluck Jonathan—Otuoke in Ogbia local government area—was equally submerged in water.

A multifaceted approach to mitigation would take into account actions like limiting or prohibiting new or inappropriate development or activities in the flood plain, removing certain structures from the floodway, flood-proofing flood plain structures, installing structural safeguards like levees, dams, and constructed channels, regulating land use practices within the basin, and implementing flood forecasting and warning systems linked with response mechanisms (Petry, 2022). Rarely is there just one way to reduce and manage risk, but rather a variety of approaches, from developing and enforcing regulations to building infrastructure to creating programs for predictions, alerts, and responses (United Nations, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Floods have caused numerous schools to close, student dropouts, property destruction, infrastructure damage, and a temporary halt to formal education (Achoka & Maiyo, 2022). Education is essential during times of crisis and can both save and preserve lives by offering mental, emotional, and cognitive safety (Richardson, 2022). Despite the fact that flooding occurs rather frequently in Nigeria during the rainy season, particularly in Southern Nigeria, this year's flooding disasters in Bayelsa State have had disastrous impacts on many Nigerians. According to official government statistics, more than 600 people have died nationwide and 1.3 million others have been forced to abandon their homes. Humanitarian organizations worry that the floods may lead to a health emergency, and Nigeria has already experienced an increase in cholera cases as a result of the country's widespread flooding. More than 2.5 million people in Nigeria require humanitarian assistance, 60% of whom are children and students, and are more vulnerable to waterborne illnesses, drowning, and hunger as a result of the worst floods in a decade, according to UNICEF (UNICEF, 2022). Bayelsa is one of the worst hit states in Nigeria, apart from the potential health risks, residents have had to confront the ripple effect of the devastating floods through skyrocketed prices of foodstuff, petrol, kerosene, and other essential commodities.

In Bayelsa State, when floods occur schools are either closed, marooned or partially submerged in flood waters and this makes the roads bridges and footpaths impassable for students and teachers. Accessing the schools

become almost impossible as both teachers and learners have challenges wading through the flood waters. The school may be abandoned for some time as learners and teachers are forced to transfer for safety to other schools or drop out completely due to inaccessible schools (Lay, Sanjaya, Ma, Anisur & Mdzakir, 2022). At times the schools are moved to higher grounds but since they are surrounded by lowlands, they become inaccessible because they are flooded or partially submerged. Therefore, it is with these stated problems, that the researcher has seen a greater need to find out the Effects of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the Effects of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Examine the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. To what extent does 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent does 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference between mean opinion scores of male and female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean opinion scores of male and female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive research design. 1,941 teachers in the nine educational zone of the State, constituted the population. A sample size of 332 participants took part in the study. This sample was randomly selected from a population of 1,941 subjects. The rationale for the use of the sample was justified by applying the Yamane's (1967) formula to the population of 1,941 to obtain a minimum sample size of 332. The major research instrument that was used for the study is the questionnaire titled: —Effects of 2022 Flooding on Academic Activities of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State Questionnaire (EFAASPSBSQ). The Likert methods of summated ratings were used in drafting the questionnaire for the study. Each item in the cluster is constructed on a – 4-point rating scale of very high extent (VHE), high extent (HE), low extent (LE) and very low extent (VLE) weighted 4-1 respectively. The instrument was validated by the experts in Educational Foundation and Measurement and Evaluation departments from the Rivers State University. The test-retest method was applied to ensure that the instrument is reliable. The instruments were administered to respondents in secondary schools outside Bayelsa State, who were not part of the study. The results were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to ascertain the co-efficient at 0.80. Out of 332 copies of the questionnaire administered to the respondents, 330 was retrieved and used for the study. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested using the z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. When the calculated z was less than the critical z of ± 1.96 the null hypothesis was accepted but when the calculated z was more than the Critical z of ± 1.96 the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld.

RESULT

Research Question. 1: To what extent does 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Teacher (Male) N= 180		Teacher (Female) N=150		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
1.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about road damages which affect students' attendance in school.	4.03	0.56	4.11	0.64	4.07	0.60	VHE
2.	Most students face challenge of fear when travelling across rivers to school due to flooding, and it affect the attendance in school.	4.05	0.92	3.96	0.96	4.01	0.94	VHE
3.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa brought about destruction and closed down of schools in some educational Zone of the state.	4.32	1.22	4.35	1.17	4.34	1.19	VHE
4.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa affected teachers, from attending schools, especially teachers, who stay far from the schools they teach, and it as well affect the student's attendance to school.	3.14	0.73	3.17	0.72	3.16	0.72	HE
5.	2022 flooding affected many homes of students and displaced some far away from their schools and this affected their attendance and closure of schools in the various LGAs of the State.	4.50	1.02	4.55	0.97	4.53	1.00	VHE
Aggregate Mean/SD for male and female teachers		4.01	0.89	4.03	0.89	4.02	0.89	VHE

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Table 1, in response to research question 1 which states to what extent does 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State had the following opinion scores for both male and female teachers. Mean scores of the male teachers to questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were 4.03, 4.05, 4.32, 3.14 and 4.50 with standard deviations of 0.56, 0.92, 1.22, 0.73 and 1.02 while the mean scores of the female teachers were 4.11, 3.96, 4.35, 3.17 and 4.55 with standard deviations of 0.64, 0.96, 1.17, 0.72 and 0.97. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female teachers were 4.07, 4.01, 4.34, 3.16 and 4.53; with standard deviation of 0.60, 0.94, 1.19, 0.72 and 1.00 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Question. 2: To what extent does 2022 floods affect student’s classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the extent 2022 floods affect student’s classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Teacher (Male) N= 180		Teacher (Female) N=150		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
6.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about loss of learning hours and it affects the quality of education and lack of classroom participation by students.	3.70	0.88	3.75	0.84	3.73	0.86	HE
7.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about destructions of school buildings and it affected student’s classroom participation.	4.35	1.16	4.41	1.11	4.38	1.14	VHE
8.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about loss of learning facilities in schools within the various LGAs of the State.	3.68	1.61	3.74	1.48	3.71	1.54	HE
9.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State affected the academic calendar of schools, brought about halt in classroom activities of the students.	3.57	0.93	3.63	0.90	3.60	0.92	HE
10.	2022 flooding in Bayelsa State affected many students from traveling outside the State to participated on academic related activities of schools, such as school related competitions during the Christmas season.	3.72	0.85	3.77	0.82	3.75	0.83	HE
Aggregate Mean/SD for male and female students		3.80	1.17	3.86	1.30	4.56	1.06	VHE

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Table 2, in response to research question 2 which states to what extent does 2022 floods affect student’s classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State, had the following opinion scores for both male and female teachers. Mean scores of the male teachers to questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were 3.70, 4.35, 3.68, 3.57 and 3.72 with standard deviations of 0.88, 1.16, 1.61, 0.93 and 0.85 while the mean scores of the female teachers were 3.75, 4.41, 3.74, 3.63 and 3.77 with standard deviation of 0.84, 1.11, 1.48, 0.90 and 0.82. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female teachers were 3.73, 4.38, 3.71, 3.60 and 3.75; with standard deviation of 0.86, 1.14, 1.54, 0.92 and 0.83 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that 2022 floods affect student’s classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between mean opinion scores of male and female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Male Teachers	180	4.01	0.89					Failed to reject
Female Teachers	150	4.03	0.89	328	0.99	±1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Tables 3, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.99 which was less than the z- critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 328, since the z-calculated (0.99) was less than the z-tabulated (±1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of Male and Female teachers on the extent to which 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between mean opinion scores of male and female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on the Extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Male Teachers	180	3.80	1.17					Failed to reject
Female Teachers	150	3.86	1.03	328	0.36	±1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Table 4, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of Male and Female SS2 teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.36 which was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 328, since the z-calculated (0.36) was less than the z- tabulated (±1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of

Male and Female teachers on the extent to which 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of 2022 floods on students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

The discussion in this study was done according to the findings of this study. The null hypothesis in table 3, was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of Male and Female teachers on the extent to which extent 2022 floods affect students' attendance in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result in Table 1, indicate that, 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about road damages which affect students' attendance in school. Most students face challenge of fear when travelling across rivers to school due to flooding, and it affect the attendance in school. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa brought about destruction and closed down of schools in some educational Zone of the state. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa affected teachers, from attending schools, especially teachers, who stay far from the schools they teach, and it as well affect the student's attendance to school. 2022 flooding affected many homes of students and displaced some far away from their schools and this affected their attendance and closure of schools in the various LGAs of the State. The findings also support the view of Carolyn et al (2022), flooding has many impacts. It damages property and endangers the lives of humans and other species. Rapid water runoff causes soil erosion and concomitant sediment deposition elsewhere (such as further downstream or down a coast). The spawning grounds for fish and other wild life habitats can become polluted or completely destroyed and some prolonged high floods can delay traffic in areas that lack elevated roadways.

Effect of 2022 floods on student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State.

The null hypothesis in table 4, was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of Male and Female teachers on the extent 2022 floods affect student's classroom participation in Public Secondary Schools in Bayelsa State. The result in Table 2, indicate that, 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about loss of learning hours and it affects the quality of education and lack of classroom participation by students. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about destructions of school buildings and it affected student's classroom participation. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State brought about loss of learning facilities in schools within the various LGAs of the State. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State affected the academic calendar of schools, brought about halt in classroom activities of the students. 2022 flooding in Bayelsa State affected many students from traveling outside the State to participate on academic related activities of schools, such as school related competitions during the Christmas season. The findings also support the view of Prasad (2021) opined that heavy rainfall is one of the major causes of seasonal floods. The level of water in rivers or lakes rises due to heavy rainfall. When the level of water rises above the riverbanks or dams, the water starts overflowing, this results to floods. The water overflows to the areas adjoining to the rivers, lakes or dams, causing floods or deluge. The flood water causes havoc and great destruction in the areas where it flows and occurs more in the regions that get heavy rainfall. This is in line with Abbott, 2021, who suggested that other seasonal weather conditions can also cause floods whereby the September of 1982, large amounts of rain fell in Utah, followed by heavy winter snows and in May, an unexpected heat wave melted the snow, causing water to cascade down the mountain slopes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that floods not only make learning inaccessible for learners and teachers, they close schools, destroy infrastructure, displace families and increase disease outbreak schools are also used as shelter for displaced families. There is need to shift from reaction to preparedness strategy with particular focus on floods. During floods quality education provides physical, psychological and cognitive

protection that can ensure dignity, sustain and save lives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Schools should engage qualified professionals to assess school buildings, design, construct and maintain school facilities to be resilient in the face of recurrent floods and other weather-related disasters.
2. Disaster risk reduction should be integrated in the syllabus. Principals, teachers and students should undergo annual training on disaster risk reduction.
3. The States governments should sensitize the communities on insuring educational institutions.
4. The ministry of education should ensure that the safety standards manual requirements are implemented in the schools.

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PICTURAL VIEWS OF AFFECTED AREAS IN BAYELSA STATE BY THE 2022 FLOOD DISASTER

Bayelsa Airport Road, Yenagoa 2022

Flooded Okodi Community, Bayelsa State 2022

Flooded sections around some neighbourhood in Bayelsa State, 2022

School half submerged in floodwaters in Bayelsa, 2022

School gate taken over by floodwaters in Bayelsa, 2022